

Ionic Equilibria in Tri-Bivalent Salts and Corresponding Heats of Dissociation : I. Aluminium Sulphate

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The dissociation constants of aluminium sulphate $\text{AlSO}_4^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Al}^{3+} + \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ and $\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_2^- \rightleftharpoons \text{AlSO}_4^+ + \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ have been determined from the study of the cell;

where Q.H. stands for quinhydrone. The values of $[\text{H}^+]$, $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$, $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$, $[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}]$, $[\text{Al}^{3+}]$, $[\text{AlSO}_4^+]$ and $[\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-]$ are found by method of successive approximations from (i) the e.m.f. of the cell, (ii) the apparent second dissociation constant of sulphuric acid and apparent solubility product of mercurous sulphate as functions of ionic strength and (iii) relationship governing $[\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-]$, $[\text{AlSO}_4^+]$, $[\text{Al}^{3+}]$.

With these values of concentrations at various ionic strengths, thermodynamic dissociation constants K_2 of $\text{AlSO}_4^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Al}^{3+} + \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ have been found to be 0.0251, 0.0178, 0.0126 and 0.0083 at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35° respectively and K_1 of $\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_2^- \rightleftharpoons \text{AlSO}_4^+ + \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ to be 0.3162, 0.1585 and 0.0891 at 15°, 25° and 35° respectively. From these values of K_2 and K_1 the heats of dissociation (ΔH) of (i) $\text{AlSO}_4^+ = \text{Al}^{3+} + \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ and (ii) $\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_2^- = \text{AlSO}_4^+ + \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ come out to be -5,700 cal./mole and -10,900 cal./mole respectively.

With the use of apparent dissociation constants as functions of ionic strength, and combination of some cells it has been possible to determine the dissociation constants of $\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-$ and AlSO_4^+ in aqueous medium.

EXPERIMENTAL

In the present investigation the dissociation constants of AlSO_4^+ and $\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-$ have been determined by measuring the e.m.f. of the cell;

As is evident from the design of the cell, there is no liquid junction potential. The bridge has been used to avoid mixing of quinhydrone with mercurous sulphate. Sulphuric acid and aluminium sulphate used were of analytical grade. Double distilled water was used in making all solutions. Stock solution of sulphuric acid was prepared and standardised against borax¹. Stock solution of aluminium sulphate in sulphuric acid was prepared and aluminium was determined volumetrically as oxinate². All solutions were prepared at the experimental

1. A. I. Vogel; Quantitative Inorganic Analysis, (Third Edn.) 1962, 238.
2. A. I. Vogel, Quantitative Inorganic Analysis, (Third Edn.) 1962, 387

temperatures. For the preparation of mercurous sulphate, the method of Hulett³ was followed. Analytical grade (Renal, Budapest) quinhydrone was recrystallised and dried following the method of Harned and Wright⁴. Pre-saturated nitrogen gas was used to remove air from the solutions in the cells. The temperature of the air thermostat was constant within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. The e.m.f. values given in the tables are mean of duplicate experiments which seldom differed from one another by 0.1 mv and never differed by more than 0.15 mv. The experimental data concerning dissociation constants, (i) of $\text{AlSO}_4^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Al}^{3+} + \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ are given in Table I to IV and (ii) of $\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_2^- \rightleftharpoons \text{AlSO}_4^+ + \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ in Tables V to VII. Stoichiometric concentration in gm. moles/litre are indicated by $[\]_T$, $\frac{[\text{Al}^{3+}][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]}{[\text{AlSO}_4^+]}$ by $K_2(\text{A})$

$\frac{[\text{AlSO}_4^+][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]}{[\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-]}$ by $K_1(\text{A})$, and $\frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]}{[\text{HSO}_4^-]}$ by K_A . All concentrations are given in gm moles/litre.

TABLE I

Temperature 5°

Mixture of		E in volt	$\frac{[\text{H}^+]}{\times 10^3}$	$\frac{[\text{HSO}_4^-]}{\times 10^4}$	$\frac{[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]}{\times 10^4}$	$\frac{[\text{Al}^{3+}]}{\times 10^4}$	$\frac{[\text{AlSO}_4^+]}{\times 10^4}$	$\frac{[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}]}{\times 10^4}$	$\mu \times 10^4$	$\log K_2(\text{A}) - \frac{1}{12A} \sqrt{\mu}$
$\frac{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4}{[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]_T}$	$\frac{\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3}{[\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3]_T}$									
0.000864	0.001152	0.14770	1.600	1.27	26.84	7.85	15.09	5.61	116.4	$\bar{4}.51$
0.000972	0.001296	0.14442	1.790	1.49	23.23	7.04	18.88	5.35	118.1	4.38
0.001080	0.001440	0.14134	1.985	1.75	29.98	6.53	22.27	5.08	121.5	$\bar{4}.29$
0.001296	0.001728	0.13607	2.363	2.29	33.24	5.29	29.27	4.65	127.2	$\bar{4}.11$
0.001512	0.002016	0.13142	2.728	2.96	37.79	5.46	34.86	4.21	141.1	$\bar{4}.07$

TABLE II

Temperature 15°

Mixture of		E in volt.	$\frac{[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]}{\times 10^4}$	$\frac{[\text{Al}^{3+}]}{\times 10^4}$	$\frac{[\text{AlSO}_4^+]}{\times 10^4}$	$\mu \times 10^4$	$\log K_2(\text{A}) - \frac{1}{12A} \sqrt{\mu}$
$\frac{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4}{[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]_T}$	$\frac{\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3}{[\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3]_T}$						
0.000864	0.001152	0.15681	25.09	6.59	16.45	109.8	$\bar{4}.37$
0.001080	0.001440	0.15011	23.79	5.92	22.88	118.1	$\bar{4}.22$
0.001296	0.001728	0.14470	32.05	4.87	29.69	124.4	$\bar{4}.05$
0.001512	0.002016	0.14012	35.28	3.84	36.48	131.0	$\bar{5}.88$
0.001728	0.002304	0.13610	39.03	3.46	42.62	141.3	$\bar{5}.79$

3. G. A. Hulett, *Phys. Rev.*, 1911, **32**, 257.4. H. S. Harned and D. D. Wright, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 4849.

TABLE III

Temperature 25°

Mixture of $\frac{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \text{ and } \text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3}{[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]_T [\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3]_T}$		E in volt	$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] \times 10^4$	$[\text{Al}^{3+}] \times 10^4$	$[\text{AlSO}_4^+] \times 10^4$	$\mu \times 10^4$	$\log K_2(\text{A}) - \frac{1}{12A\sqrt{\mu}}$
0.000864	0.001152	0.16604	24.38	6.48	16.56	109.8	$\bar{4}.34$
0.000972	0.001296	0.16241	26.35	6.37	19.55	114.9	$\bar{4}.28$
0.001080	0.001440	0.15930	27.71	5.63	23.17	116.5	$\bar{4}.17$
0.001296	0.001728	0.15376	31.10	4.95	29.61	124.4	$\bar{4}.03$
0.001512	0.002016	0.14901	35.44	5.40	34.92	138.8	$\bar{4}.02$
0.001728	0.002304	0.14501	38.77	4.84	41.23	147.6	$\bar{5}.92$

TABLE IV

Temperature 35°

Mixture of $\frac{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \text{ and } \text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3}{[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]_T [\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3]_T}$		E in volt	$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] \times 10^4$	$[\text{Al}^{3+}] \times 10^4$	$[\text{AlSO}_4^+] \times 10^4$	$\mu \times 10^4$	$\log K_2(\text{A}) - \frac{1}{12A\sqrt{\mu}}$
0.000864	0.001152	0.17409	25.06	7.74	15.30	117.7	$\bar{4}.43$
0.001080	0.001440	0.16711	29.38	8.16	20.64	131.1	$\bar{4}.35$
0.001296	0.001728	0.16150	33.64	8.64	25.92	145.3	$\bar{4}.30$
0.001512	0.002016	0.15679	37.75	9.10	31.22	159.3	$\bar{4}.26$
0.001728	0.002304	0.15286	40.15	7.75	38.33	163.1	$\bar{4}.11$

TABLE V

Temperature 15°

Mixture of $\frac{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \text{ and } \text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3}{[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]_T [\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3]_T}$		E in volt	$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] \times 10^4$	$[\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-] \times 10^4$	$[\text{AlSO}_4^+] \times 10^4$	$\mu \times 10^4$	$\log K_1(\text{A}) - \frac{1}{4A\sqrt{\mu}}$
0.002160	0.002880	0.13005	41.49	2.67	54.93	142.0	$\bar{2}.69$
0.002376	0.003168	0.12751	43.03	5.38	57.98	149.9	$\bar{2}.42$
0.002592	0.003456	0.12503	45.65	6.84	62.28	159.9	$\bar{2}.37$
0.002808	0.003744	0.12282	47.77	8.83	66.06	168.9	$\bar{2}.29$
0.004320	0.005760	0.11206	52.52	33.89	81.31	213.6	$\bar{3}.81$
0.006480	0.008640	0.10254	53.50	76.44	96.36	266.4	$\bar{3}.50$
0.008640	0.011520	0.09576	55.14	118.12	112.28	320.4	$\bar{3}.36$
0.010800	0.014400	0.09154	49.56	170.58	117.42	360.9	$\bar{3}.50$

TABLE VI

Temperature 25°

Mixture of		E in volt	[SO ₄ ²⁻] × 10 ⁴	[Al(SO ₄) ₂ ⁻] × 10 ⁴	[AlSO ₄ ⁺] × 10 ⁴	μ × 10 ⁴	log K ₁ (A) - 4A√μ
H ₂ SO ₄ and Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	[H ₂ SO ₄] _T [Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃] _T						
0.00216	0.00288	0.13920	38.22	4.21	53.39	137.1	2.45
0.00432	0.00576	0.12046	51.13	30.73	84.47	212.0	3.85
0.00648	0.00864	0.10996	58.27	62.63	110.17	276.4	3.67
0.00864	0.01152	0.10255	64.63	94.43	135.97	339.2	3.59
0.01080	0.01440	0.09752	62.01	139.29	148.71	385.1	3.42

TABLE VII

Temperature 35°

Mixture of		E in volt	[SO ₄ ²⁻] × 10 ⁴	[Al(SO ₄) ₂ ⁻] × 10 ⁴	[AlSO ₄] × 10 ⁴	μ × 10 ⁴	log K ₁ (A) - 4A√μ
H ₂ SO ₄ and Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	[H ₂ SO ₄] _T [Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃] _T						
0.00216	0.00288	0.14740	34.72	6.59	51.01	132.2	2.19
0.00432	0.00576	0.12375	42.29	38.45	76.75	197.1	3.63
0.00648	0.00864	0.11900	40.75	82.13	90.67	245.8	3.28
0.00864	0.01152	0.11150	44.27	118.26	112.14	303.2	3.26
0.01080	0.01440	0.10561	48.16	152.98	135.02	361.1	3.23

DISCUSSION

The e.m.f. of the cell ;

is given by

$$E = E^0 - \frac{2.303RT}{2F} \log [H^+]^2 [SO_4^{2-}] + \frac{2.303RT}{F} \times 3A\sqrt{\mu} - \frac{2.303RTB\mu}{2F} \quad \dots (1)$$

The values of E⁰ and B, taking the solubility of Hg₂SO₄ into account, have been reported earlier⁵. From the e.m.f. the cell, E⁰, B, A and an arbitrary value of μ, the corresponding value of [H⁺]²[SO₄²⁻] is calculated from equation (1). As explained earlier^{6,7}

$$\log K_A = \log \frac{[H^+][SO_4^{2-}]}{[HSO_4^-]} = \log K + 4A\sqrt{\mu} - \beta\mu \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\log f \text{Hg}_2 \text{f SO}_4 = 2 \log f \text{SO}_4 = -8A\sqrt{\mu} + 2\beta\mu \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\log K_{sp} = \log [Hg_2^{2+}][SO_4^{2-}] - 8A\sqrt{\mu} + 2\beta\mu \quad \dots (4)$$

5. L. Sharma and B. Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 379.

6. L. Sharma and B. Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 241.

7. L. Sharma and B. Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 193.

It has also been explained⁷ that the value of β in equation (3) and (4) is the same as in equation (2). Since A is known from Debye-Huckel equation and the values of K and β are given in earlier papers⁶, the value of $\frac{[H^+][SO_4^{2-}]}{[HSO_4^-]}$ corresponding to the arbitrary value of μ is calculated from equation (2). Dividing the value of $[H^+]^2[SO_4^{2-}]$ by that of $\frac{[H^+][SO_4^{2-}]}{[HSO_4^-]}$, we get the value of $[H^+][HSO_4^-]$. If α is the degree of dissociation of HSO_4^- and c_1 is the stoichiometric concentration of H_2SO_4 , then $[H^+][HSO_4^-] = c_1^2(1-\alpha^2)$. So we can determine the corresponding values of α , $[H^+]$ and $[HSO_4^-]$. The corresponding $[SO_4^{2-}]$ (from H_2SO_4 , Hg_2SO_4 and $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ together) can be determined by dividing the value of $[H^+]^2[SO_4^{2-}]$ by that of $[H^+]^2$. Since K_{sp} is known, the corresponding $[Hg_2^{2+}]$ can be calculated from equation (4). The corresponding values of $[Al^{3+}]$, $[AlSO_4^+]$ and $[Al(SO_4)_2^-]$ present in aluminium sulphate solution are calculated as explained below. It is assumed that when $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ is dissolved in dilute H_2SO_4 , it dissociates as follows :

In a solution of aluminium sulphate in sulphuric acid (a) total aluminium $[Al]_T$ will be the sum of aluminium in various forms and (b) the sum of positive charges will be equal to the sum of negative charges. It follows :

$$[Al]_T = [Al^{3+}] + [AlSO_4^+] + [Al(SO_4)_2^-] \quad \dots (5)$$

$$3[Al^{3+}] + [H^+] + [AlSO_4^+] = [Al(SO_4)_2^-] + 2[SO_4^{2-}] + [HSO_4^-] \quad \dots (6)$$

On adding equation (5) and (6), we get,

$$2[Al^{3+}] - 2[Al(SO_4)_2^-] = 2[SO_4^{2-}] + [HSO_4^-] - [H^+] - [Al]_T \quad \dots (7)$$

Similarly, multiplying equation (5) by 3 and then adding to equation (6), we get,

$$2[AlSO_4^+] = 3[Al]_T + [H^+] - 4[Al(SO_4)_2^-] - 2[SO_4^{2-}] - [HSO_4^-] \quad \dots (8)$$

In very dilute solution of $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ in sulphuric acid $[Al(SO_4)_2^-]$ will be negligible. Hence the values of $[Al^{3+}]$ and $[AlSO_4^+]$ corresponding to the arbitrary value of μ are calculated from equations (7) and (8) respectively assuming that $[Al(SO_4)_2^-] = 0$. A new value of μ is now found out from $\mu = \frac{1}{2}[H^+] + \frac{1}{2}[HSO_4^-] + 2[SO_4^{2-}] + 2[Hg_2^{2+}] + \frac{1}{2}[AlSO_4^+] + 9/2[Al^{3+}]$ and the whole process is repeated till the values of $[H^+]$, $[HSO_4^-]$, $[SO_4^{2-}]$, $[Hg_2^{2+}]$, $[AlSO_4^+]$, $[Al^{3+}]$ μ become constant within experimental error. In the above cases,

$$\frac{[Al^{3+}][SO_4^{2-}]}{[AlSO_4^+]} \times \frac{f Al \times f SO_4}{f AlSO_4} = K_2$$

or
$$\log \frac{[Al^{3+}][SO_4^{2-}]}{[AlSO_4^+]} - 12A\sqrt{\mu} = \log K_2 - b_2/\mu \quad \dots (9)$$

On increasing the concentration of $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ and H_2SO_4 the value of $[Al^{3+}]$ goes on decreasing and becomes eventually zero. The values of $[Al(SO_4)_2^-]$ and $[AlSO_4^+]$ are calculated

from equations (7) and (8) respectively, $[Al^{3+}] = 0$. The value of μ is then calculated from $\mu = \frac{1}{2}[H^+] + \frac{1}{2}[HSO_4^-] + 2[SO_4^{2-}] + 2[Hg_2^{2+}] + \frac{1}{2}[Al(SO_4)_2^-] + \frac{1}{2}[AlSO_4^+]$. The whole process is again repeated till the values of $[H^+]$, $[HSO_4^-]$, $[SO_4^{2-}]$, $[Hg_2^{2+}]$, $[Al(SO_4)_2^-]$, $[AlSO_4^+]$ and μ become constant within experimental error. In these cases;

$$\frac{[AlSO_4^+][SO_4^{2-}]}{[Al(SO_4)_2^-]} \times \frac{f AlSO_4 \times f SO_4}{f Al(SO_4)_2} = K_1$$

or,
$$\log \frac{[AlSO_4^+][SO_4^{2-}]}{[Al(SO_4)_2^-]} - 4A\sqrt{\mu} = \log K_1 - b_1\mu \quad \dots (10)$$

The data thus obtained are given in tables I to IV in the case of K_2 and in V to VII in the case of K_1 . The values of K_2 and K_1 can be determined by plotting L.H.S. of equations (9) and (10) respectively against μ taking the necessary precautions as in earlier paper⁸. A straight line is obtained in each case which when extrapolated to $\mu = 0$ gives $\log K_2$ in one case and $\log K_1$ in another. The thermodynamic dissociation constants thus found are given below :

	5°	15°	25°	35°
$K_1 \times 10$	—	3.16	1.59	0.89
$K_2 \times 10^3$	2.51	1.78	1.26	0.83

It may be pointed out that the mean value, for the instability constant of $AlSO_4^+ \rightleftharpoons Al^{3+} + SO_4^{2-}$, determined by an entirely different method⁹ at 29–30° is $9.08 (\pm 0.44) \times 10^{-3}$ and is of the same order as our values.

The heats of dissociation (ΔH) of (i) $AlSO_4^+ = Al^{3+} + SO_4^{2-}$ and (ii) $Al(SO_4)_2^- = AlSO_4^+ + SO_4^{2-}$ have also been calculated by plotting our values of (i) $\log K_2$ and (ii) $\log K_1$ against $1/T$. The values of ΔH for (i) and (ii) come out to be $-5,700 \pm 100$ cal./mole and $10,900 \pm$ cal./mole respectively.

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8. L. Sharma, G. Sahu and B. Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 580.
9. R. K. Nanda and S. Aditya, *Z. Physik Chem.*, 1962, **35**, 140.